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RF Measurement on a Superconducting Accelerating Cavity

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1 Introduction

This experiment is dedicated to conducting radiofrequency (RF) measurements on a superconducting accelerating cavity. The details related to the examined cavity are outlined hereafter (See Figure 1). The cavity in question is a half-wave resonator, specifically a Spoke resonator, constructed from bulk Niobium. The essential RF parameters of the cavity are explained in the table below (See Table 1).

Figure 1: This figure shows the studied cavity in this experiment at the IJClab, which is a half-wave spoke resonator made of bulk Niobium.

2 Presentation of facilities

2.1 The principle of operation of an accelerating cavity

An accelerating cavity uses an electric field stored in radio frequency resonators to transfer energy and accelerate charged particles. It is designed to resonate at a specific resonant frequency. This is achieved by optimizing the shape to support a standing wave of electromagnetic fields within the cavity. It is typically a metallic structure and has a beam pipe that allows the particle beam to pass through and other apertures to monitor and position the beam. There is also an antenna or power-coupler that is inserted into the cavity to couple the field into the cavity, and hence to the beam.

Parameters	Simulated value
Frequency F_0 (MHz)	352
R/Q (Ω)	384
G (Ω)	85
β_{opt}	0.3
Gap number (Ng)	4
$L_{acc} = Ng * \beta_{opt} * c / F / 2$ (m)	0.511
E_{pk} / E_{acc}	4.08
$B_{pk} / E_{acc} (mT / MV / m)$	10.25
Total cavity length (m)	0.76

Table 1: The fundamental characteristics of the studied cavity. [1]

The shape of the cavity is optimized to support the electric field, $\vec{E}$, and to minimize the effect of the magnetic field $\vec{B}$ since the power coupled to the beam only comes from the electric field. The shape of the cavity is also optimized to avoid multipacting, which is the resonance of electrons, causing an avalanche that drains the RF power, making it impossible to increase the gradient. The investigated cavity is a cylindrical spoke resonator featuring two horizontally inserted spokes and one vertically oriented spoke. This structural configuration results in the compartmentalization of the cavity into four distinct spaces, each characterized by opposing accelerating fields.

2.2 Superconductivity in RF cavities

One of the main constraints on the amount of power that is coupled to the beam comes from the dissipation in the form of heat due to the surface resistance of the material used for the cavity. Thus, the ideal material for superconducting cavities should exhibit a high critical temperature, a high critical field, and, above all, a low surface resistance. This is one of the main reasons why Niobium is a top contender for the production of cavities. Copper could also be chosen due to its high electrical conductivity with a thin film of Nb coated on top. But when copper is used as a material for the cavity, although the dissipation is less, it is higher (almost a million times) as compared to Nb SRFs (Superconducting Radio Frequency cavities) which have dissipation of about 2 Watts. Due to this, copper cavities can only be operated in pulsed operations, where power is dissipated for a very short time, while CW operation is only possible in SRFs.

2.3 Types of cavities:

The three types of cavities presented at the IJCLab were classified based on the frequency supported to stand in the cavity and the β value. The shapes are tweaked to achieve desired values of β , suited for different applications. The properties specific to each are listed in Table 2, and the corresponding schematics are shown in Figure 2. The full-wave cavity is the most efficient for acceleration.

Type	β	Acc. Gradient (MV/m)	f range (MHz)	Applications
Full-wave	0.5 - 1	30	500 - 4000	LINACS - high energy acceleration
Half-wave	0.2 - 0.5	10-15	200 - 500	SRF - research & medical
Quarter-wave	0.0 - 0.2	< 10	50 - 200	RF devices & communication

Table 2: Types of cavities presented at the IJCLab.

Figure 2: Simple sketches of (a) Full-wave resonator, (b) Half-wave resonator, (c) Quarter-wave. Blue: The electric field direction, Red: The magnetic field direction.

2.4 Steps of preparation of a superconducting cavity

A contaminated or dirty cavity can emit electrons out of its surface causing the Bremsstrahlung effect and producing a flux of electrons and photons in the system. Field emission is also a possibility. This is not only a safety hazard but also makes the efforts of superconductivity futile. There are hence several steps to be followed before the cavity is placed in the vertical cryostat for cooling.

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1. The cavity is started by being weighed, followed by ultrasonic cleaning.
 2. To remove the defects and impurities caused during the transport of the cavity, it is first placed in a Buffer Chemical Polishing (BCP) that removes about 200 microns of the material, originally 3 mm. At the end of this procedure, a crystalline structure is obtained. This process lasts for about 8 hours. This procedure is called etching. The acid mixture contains Phosphoric, Nitric, and Hydrofluoric acid to the ratio of 2.4:1:1. Typical average etching rate is $0.5 \mu\text{m} / \text{minute}$.
 3. Subsequently, it is rinsed with ultra-pure water ($18.2 \text{ M}\Omega\text{cm}$) to remove chemical residues. It contains a high-pressure rinsing system at 100 Bar (400 L/h), and also the temperature and the humidity are properly controlled. Then, it is placed in a clean room to let it dry.
 4. Then, a furnace is used where heat is applied to remove the hydrogen from the surface, preventing the formation of Niobium Hydride, which is not a superconducting material. This can be done either at 600 degrees for 10 hours or 800 degrees for 3 hours.
 5. After the furnace, it is again etched quickly to remove the oxygen from the surface.
 6. The final step is to be kept in a clean room, where it is later also assembled. The cavity can then be placed in a vertical cryostat.

3 RF coupling measurement

The measurement of RF coupling is not only essential for the regular operation of power transfer but also during qualification tests where the cryogenic performance of the system is evaluated. In this section, we determine the optimal lengths of the incident and transmitted antennas. The scattering parameters, denoted as S_{ij} , are defined as shown in Equation 1.

$$S_{ij} = \frac{V_{out,i}}{V_{in,j}} \quad (1)$$

It represents the ratio of the output potential $V_{out,i}$ measured at port j to the input potential $V_{in,j}$ applied at port i . In other words, it quantifies the relationship between the input and output voltages for a specific port configuration.

The quality factor is defined as the ratio of the energy stored in the resonator to the energy lost per cycle of the resonator.

Critical coupling refers to a specific condition where the amount of energy absorbed by the resonator is equal to the amount of energy radiated or transmitted out of the system. That is, the resonator is perfectly matched to its surroundings, leading to efficient power transfer. In particular, the unloaded quality factor (Q_0) is equal to the external one (Q_{ext}).

$$Q_{ext} = Q_0, \quad (2)$$

The areas of under and over-coupling can be defined in terms of the length of the antenna, as shown in Figure 3. A possible way to determine if we are in the under or over-couple regime is to vary the length of the antenna and observe how the points in the plot are displaced. An alternative definition of the two regimes is obtained by defining the coupling factor β (presented in Equation 12), the case of critical coupling is when $\beta = 1$; if over-coupled ($\beta > 1$) the signs on the top must be used, if under-coupled ($\beta < 1$), the signs on the bottom should be used. Under-coupling is characterized by weak coupling, where most of the power is reflected; in over-coupling we have strong coupling, and the emitted power is large.

In order to facilitate the acceleration of the beam, it is necessary to energize the resonant cavity. Commonly employed power sources for this purpose encompass klystrons, and tetrodes, among others. It is most efficient to match the load (cavity+beam) to the power source. Using the circuit analog for a resonant cavity mode, the following relationship can be derived, whereas Q_L is the loaded quality factor and Q_t is the transmitted quality factor.

$$\frac{1}{Q_L} = \frac{1}{Q_0} + \frac{1}{Q_{ext}} + \frac{1}{Q_t} \quad (3)$$

In Table 3, the resonant frequency, bandwidth, Q_{ext} , Q_t , and the reflected (S_{11}) and transmitted (S_{21}) signals for different antenna lengths are presented. Figure 4 presents the evolution of Q_{ext} .

By changing the antenna length it was noted that the critical coupling takes place at a length of 14 cm. Extrapolation of the curve fitting led to the determination that it is associated with a Q_t value of 1175682.

At critical coupling, and with Equations 2 and 3, the following equation can be derived.

Figure 3: Areas of under-coupling and over-coupling in terms of the length of the antenna. (Note that, the length is arbitrary in this figure).

Figure 4: The behavior of $Q_i = Q_{\text{ext}}$ against the length of the antenna. Notice that the value is approximately constant.

$$Q_0 = \frac{2}{\frac{1}{Q_L} - \frac{1}{Q_t}} \quad (4)$$

Using the previously obtained value of Q_t and determining the value of Q_L using the recorded data in Table 3 as 4110, Q_0 was calculated as 8249, with the aid of Equation 4.

Antenna length [cm]	Resonant frequency [MHz]	BW [kHz]	S_{11} [dB]	S_{21} [dB]	Q_{ext}	Q_t
10	354.595	111.110	-7.25	-17.03	4450.996	461914
9	354.577	87.301	-8.87	-20.79	5972.142	1325294
8	354.580	82.539	-6.75	-24.91	5885.907	3884692
7	354.581	80.952	-6.64	-33.25	5977.320	27134961
6	354.582	80.952	-6.64	-39.61	5977.337	117362792
5	354.580	81.904	-6.82	-47.14	5946.573	652546561
4	354.584	82.539	-8.61	-55.66	6266.403	4336721238
3	354.579	78.571	-9.82	-61.19	6822.921	15703307483
2	354.562	100.000	-10.82	-71.85	5506.733	1.39814×10^{11}

Table 3: Resonant frequency, bandwidth (BW), reflected (S_{11}) and transmitted S_{21} signals for different antenna lengths.

Figure 5: The behavior of the logarithmic value of Q_t against the length of the antenna. A linear curve is fitted to the data points whereas the gradient and the intercept were determined as -1.59729 [Units/ cm], and 28.4323515 [Units] respectively.

Using a power meter, the injected RF power was measured as -27.59 dBm, which corresponds to the power of 1.8238×10^{-6} W (See Equation 20). Then the stored energy in the cavity at the resonant frequency (f_0) was calculated using Equation 11, as 6.7527×10^{-12} J.

For the next part, it was considered that the triple Spoke cavity is tested at 2K and has a residual resistance of $5 \text{ n}\Omega$. Therefore, to have a critical coupling for the incident antenna, the following relationship should be satisfied: $Q_{\text{ext}} = Q_{0,2\text{K}}$. The Niobium surface resistance at 2K was calculated as $1.23 \text{ n}\Omega$, using Equation 22. The surface resistance at 2K was determined as $6.23 \text{ n}\Omega$, using Equation 21. Then using the definition of the G-factor, $Q_{0,2\text{K}}$ was determined as 1.364×10^{10} (See Equation 17). Under this condition, Equation 3 reduces into the following relationship.

$$\frac{1}{Q_t} = \frac{1}{Q_L} - \frac{2}{Q_0} \quad (5)$$

This corresponds to a value of Q_t of 4110. Then using the fitted curve presented in Figure 5 with its gradient and intercept values, the length of the antenna was determined as 15.54 cm.

To have an under-coupling of 10 for the transmitted antenna, the following relationship should be satisfied; $Q_t = 10Q_{0,2\text{K}}$. This corresponds to a value of Q_t of 1.364×10^{11} . Then following the same method explained earlier, using the fitted curve presented in Figure 5 with its gradient and intercept values, the length of the antenna was determined as 10.83 cm.

A bandwidth of 150 Hz at 2K at the resonant frequency of the cavity corresponds to a value of 2346667 for Q_L , using Equation 15. Then, using Equation 3, and neglecting Q_t , the incident coupling Q_{ext} was determined as 2347070.

4 Field flatness measurement

The field flatness measurement is done to ensure the uniformity of $\vec{E}$ amplitude throughout a multi-cell cavity. In this practical, we perform this by inserting a perturbation, which is a metallic bead in our case, into the spoke cavity. The bead could be displaced inside the cavity thanks to a motor. According to the **Slater theorem** given in 6, we expect the resonant frequency to change with the volume change in the cavity.

$$\frac{df}{f_0} = -\frac{1}{4 \cdot U} \int_{\Delta V} (\mu_0 H^2 - \varepsilon_0 E^2) dV \quad (6)$$

We start by acquiring the phase variation in time within a time sweep of 20 seconds, as the bead traverses through the cavity. The rate of change of phase can be related to the bandwidth and frequency by the equation:

$$\frac{df}{dt} = \frac{2\Delta f}{\pi} \times \frac{d\phi}{dt}$$

where Δf is the bandwidth of the mode and $d\phi/dt$ is the slope calculated using the Bode diagram presented in Figure 6.

The acquired data gives the variation of phase in time, which is then translated to a change of frequency with the position of the bead, from which the change of Electric field is extrapolated.

Figure 6: The behavior of the phase measurement against the frequency. Around the resonant frequency, this behavior is linear.

From the given information, the velocity of the bead at any given time is found using the relation:

$$v_b = \text{Scanned length} \times \frac{\text{motor speed}}{\text{Number of motor steps}} \quad (7)$$

$$v_b = 6.13 \text{ cm/s} \quad (8)$$

In Figures 7, 8, 9 the difference of frequency as a function of time, and as a function of distance along the beam axis are plotted for the first three modes.

Figure 7: (Left) This illustrates the changes in df (the difference in frequency) measured in kHz over time. (Right) This showcases the relationship between df (the difference in frequency) measured in kHz against the distance along the beam axis inside the cavity. Note that, the variation is shown for the first mode.

Figure 8: (Left) This illustrates the changes in df (the difference in frequency) measured in kHz over time. (Right) This showcases the relationship between df (the difference in frequency) measured in kHz against the distance along the beam axis inside the cavity. Note that, the variation is shown for the second mode.

Figure 9: (Left) This illustrates the changes in df (the difference in frequency) measured in kHz over time. (Right) This showcases the relationship between df (the difference in frequency) measured in kHz against the distance along the beam axis inside the cavity. Note that, the variation is shown for the third mode.

5 SRF Tuner characterization

Ensuring a precise match between the resonant frequency and the frequency of the input RF wave is a critical consideration when operating a superconducting cavity. Any disparity in frequencies can result in the cavity reflecting the power instead of effectively transferring it to the beam. Achieving this match is challenging due to fluctuations in helium pressure, used as a cryogenic medium, and other thermal effects that lead to deformation.

Here, a tuner is used to induce deformation in the cavity, utilizing two types of actuators. One is a slow actuator capable of achieving a broad range of frequency control, while the other is capable of fast control but is limited to a smaller range.

5.1 Slow tuning characterization

The first actuator is powered by a stepper motor, and a ball screw system is employed to affect a double lever arm mechanism, resulting in a significantly reduced displacement of the cavity flange along the beam axis. The specifications of the tuner are detailed in Table 4.

To prevent permanent deformation, the maximum frequency shift applied by the tuner is kept below 20 kHz. The conversion factor from micro steps executed by the motor to the displacement of the beam flange along the beam axis is given by the following conversion (See Equation 10).

Figure 10: SRF tuner schematic diagram. (Taken from the instruction manual). [1]

Table 4: The specifications of the tuner are detailed for the tuner. [1]

Attributes	Unit	Value
Stepper motor resolution	Step/turn	200
Microstepping	μ step/step	16
Planetary gear ratio		50:1
Ball screw pitch	mm	2
Double lever ratio		16

Figure 11: (Left) The frequency shift of the cavity against the motor steps, while increasing the number of steps (Blue), and decreasing the number of steps (Orange), and their average are presented in the plot. (Right) A linear curve is fitted to the region which showed a linear response. The gradient was determined as $5.07504 \times 10^{-8} \text{MHz}/\mu \text{ steps}$.

$$f = dx(\mu \text{ steps}) \quad (9)$$

$$f = \frac{200 \times 16 \times 50 \times 16}{8} = 1280000(\mu \text{ steps}) \quad (10)$$

In essence, this shows that $1\text{mm} = 1.28 \times 10^6(\mu \text{ steps})$.

The frequency shift of the cavity against the motor steps is presented in Figure 11.

5.1.1 Tuning sensitivity coefficient

Using the obtained gradient of the fitted curve (See Figure 11 [Right]), and the earlier conversion factor calculated in Equation 10 ($1\text{mm} = 1.28 \times 10^6(\mu \text{ steps})$), the tuning sensitivity coefficient is calculated 64.645 kHz/mm .

As compared to the computed cavity sensitivity which is 180 kHz/mm , the calculated value in this experiment was lower. This could happen due to two main reasons. First, when the deformation is applied to the cavity mechanically, the final metal arm is connected only to the outer layer of the cavity, not the inner layer which should essentially be deformed. Second, there were some mechanical plays (in nuts and bolts) of the lever and the arms. Hence, their effect on the net displacement was not accounted for correctly.

Table 5: The frequency was measured by increasing and decreasing the number of steps of the rotor. The average frequency was also calculated.

Step	Frequency (Increasing) (MHz)	Frequency (Decreasing) (MHz)	Average Frequency (MHz)
0	354.5515877	354.5515877	354.5515877
5000	354.5515877	354.5515877	354.5515877
10000	354.5515877	354.551429	354.5515084
15000	354.5515877	354.5515877	354.5515877
20000	354.551429	354.5515877	354.5515084
30000	354.551429	354.5515877	354.5515084
40000	354.5515877	354.5515877	354.5515877
50000	354.5512703	354.551429	354.5513497
60000	354.551429	354.551429	354.551429
70000	354.551429	354.5515877	354.5515084
80000	354.551429	354.551429	354.551429
90000	354.551429	354.5515877	354.5515084
100000	354.551429	354.551429	354.551429
110000	354.551429	354.551429	354.551429
120000	354.5515877	354.551429	354.5515084
130000	354.5515877	354.5515877	354.5515877
140000	354.5517465	354.5515877	354.5516671
150000	354.5523814	354.5517465	354.552064
160000	354.5530163	354.5520639	354.5525401
170000	354.5533338	354.5522227	354.5527783
180000	354.55381	354.5525401	354.5531751
190000	354.5541274	354.5530163	354.5535719
200000	354.5547623	354.5534925	354.5541274
210000	354.5553973	354.5539687	354.554683
220000	354.5557147	354.5546036	354.5551592
240000	354.5568258	354.5557147	354.5562703
260000	354.5580957	354.5569846	354.5575402
280000	354.5590481	354.5580957	354.5585719
300000	354.5603179	354.5590505	354.5596842

Table 6: Specifications for the Piezo actuator used in the experiment. [1]

Attributes	Unit	Value
Shape		Square
Width	mm	10
Length	mm	36
Maximum voltage	V	200
Capacitance	μF	6.73
Maximum stroke	μm	56.1

5.2 Fast tuning characterization

The second actuator, constructed from PZT ceramics, operates as a Piezo actuator capable of generating mechanical strain through electric charges. Comprising multiple ceramic plates arranged along the polarization axis and connected in parallel, the actuators exhibit the following specifications outlined in Table 6.

5.2.1 Phase measurement setup

The cavity functions similarly to a band-pass filter. By introducing a fixed-frequency signal near the resonant frequency through the forward port, we can gauge the relative phase measurement, serving as an indicator of the resonant frequency shift within the cavity.

By increasing the voltage to the Piezo actuator up to 150 V and then again decreasing back incrementally, the relative phase was measured and recorded in Table 7. Similarly, the phase was measured when increasing and decreasing the voltage applied to the actuator in steps of 50 V, to observe the hysteresis effect (See Table 8). The respective behavior is illustrated in Figure 12.

Then, by changing the frequency around the resonant frequency, the relative phase was again measured (see Table 9). The relationship between the frequency difference and the phase difference is linear since $\Delta\phi \propto \delta f$.

The behavior of the phase difference against the applied voltage is presented in Figure 13 [Left], and the behavior of the phase difference against center frequency is shown in Figure 13 [Right].

Table 7: Phase measured by increasing and decreasing the voltage applied to the actuator.

Voltage (V)	Phase (Increasing) (Degree)	Phase (Decreasing) (Degree)	Average Phase (Degree)
0	106.63	107.39	107.01
10	106.64	107.22	106.93
20	106.61	107.09	106.85
30	106.48	107.00	106.74
40	106.41	106.89	106.65
50	106.30	106.78	106.54
60	106.26	106.67	106.465
70	106.15	106.52	106.335
80	106.05	106.47	106.26
90	105.95	106.43	106.19
100	105.84	106.30	106.07
110	105.75	106.15	105.95
120	105.64	106.10	105.87
130	105.54	105.95	105.745
140	105.43	105.98	105.705

Table 8: Phase measured when increasing and decreasing voltage applied to the actuator in steps of 50 V, to observe the hysteresis effect.

Voltage (v)	Phase (Increasing) (Degree)	Phase (Decreasing) (Degree)
0	107.35	107.31
50	107.00	106.78
100	106.48	106.28
150	105.95	105.95

Table 9: Center Frequency (MHz) and Phase Data (Degree)

Center Frequency (MHz)	Phase (Degree)
354.5523814	96.27
354.5530163	96.99
354.5533338	97.29
354.55381	97.84
354.5541274	98.15
354.5547623	98.74
354.5553973	99.52
354.5557147	99.83
354.5568258	101.05
354.5580957	102.37
354.5590481	103.5
354.5603179	104.88
354.5612703	105.91

Figure 12: (Left) The behavior of the phase measured by increasing the applied voltage [Blue], and decreasing the voltage [Orange] is plotted. The average behavior is also plotted [Green]. (Right) The same behavior of the phase measured by increasing the applied voltage [Blue], and decreasing the voltage [Orange] is plotted in steps of 50V to see the effect of the hysteresis.

Figure 13: (Left) The behavior of the phase difference against the applied voltage. A linear curve is fitted to the data points whereas the gradient was determined as $0.009625[\text{Degree}/V]$. (Right) The behavior of the phase difference against center frequency. A linear curve is fitted to the data points whereas the gradient was determined as $1083.1558 \text{ Degree}/\text{MHz}$.

To determine the tuning sensitivity of the cavity due to the action of the Piezo actuator, the following calculation was carried out. Note that, for this calculation, the two gradients of the fitted curves of Figure 13 were used.

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d\phi}{dV} &= 0.009625 \left(\frac{\text{degree}}{V} \right) \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{d\phi}{df} = 1083.2 \left(\frac{\text{degree}}{\text{MHz}} \right) \\ \implies \frac{df}{dV} &= \frac{d\phi}{dV} \times \frac{df}{d\phi} = 8.886 \text{ Hz}/V \end{aligned}$$

A non-linear behavior was observed around the maximum voltage of 150 V. When a high voltage is applied to the Piezo actuator for a considerably longer time, the Piezo tends to have a deformation that lasts quite some time. Therefore, it is advised to increment and decrease the applied voltage within similar periods.

6 Conclusions

This experiment investigated the RF measurement on an SC cavity presented at the IJClab made of bulk Niobium.

RF coupling measurements were performed to have an optimal transfer of the RF power to the cavity, whereas the length of the two antennas (incident and transmitted) was sized.

Field flatness measurements were performed (by creating a disturbance of the resonant frequency) and the field amplitude inside the cavity was observed.

By using a tuner (consisting of a slow actuator and a fast actuator) that is capable of deforming the cavity slightly, the effects that might take place (due to the perturbation) were studied. Additionally, the tuner was also characterized.

7 Useful formulae

$$Q_n = \omega_0 \cdot \frac{U}{P_n} \quad (11)$$

$$\beta = \frac{1 + \rho}{1 - \rho} = \frac{1 \pm \sqrt{\frac{P_r}{P_i}}}{1 \mp \sqrt{\frac{P_r}{P_i}}} \quad (12)$$

$$Q_0 = \frac{R}{L \cdot \omega_0} = R \cdot \sqrt{\frac{C}{L}} \quad (13)$$

$$\omega_0 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{LC}} \quad (14)$$

$$\Delta F = 2 \cdot (F_{P_{\max}/2} - F_0) = \frac{F_0}{Q_L} \quad (15)$$

$$\frac{r}{Q} = \frac{\left[\int_0^L E z(z) \cdot \cos\left(\frac{\omega_0 \cdot z}{\beta \cdot c}\right) \cdot dz \right]^2}{P_c \cdot Q_0} \quad (16)$$

$$Q_0 = \frac{G}{R_s} \quad (17)$$

$$Q_i = \frac{2 \cdot Q_L}{1 \pm \sqrt{\frac{P_r}{P_i}}} \quad (18)$$

$$Q_t = 2 \cdot Q_L \cdot \frac{P_i}{P_t} \cdot \left(1 \pm \sqrt{\frac{P_r}{P_i}} \right) \quad (19)$$

$$P(\text{dBm}) = 10 \cdot \log\left(\frac{P(W)}{0.001}\right) \quad (20)$$

$$R_S = R_{BCS} + R_{\text{res}} \quad (21)$$

$$R_{BCS} = \frac{9 \cdot 10^{-5}}{T(K)} \cdot f^2(\text{GHz}) \cdot \exp\left(-\frac{16.84}{T(K)}\right) \quad (22)$$

$$\frac{df}{f_0} = -\frac{1}{4 \cdot U} \int_{\Delta V} (\mu_0 H^2 - \varepsilon_0 E^2) dV \quad (23)$$

$$\frac{df}{f_0} = \frac{-\pi r^3}{U} \cdot \epsilon_0 \cdot E_0^2 \quad (24)$$

$$V_{\text{acc}} = E_{\text{acc}} \cdot L_{\text{acc}} = \left| \int_0^L E_z(z) \cdot \cos\left(\omega_0 \cdot \frac{z}{\beta \cdot c} + \phi_{\text{sync}}\right) \cdot dz \right| \quad (25)$$

References

- [1] D. Longuevergne and N. Gandolfo, *Instruction Manual of Practical Work on Superconducting Cavity*.